

**The issue of war
in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church and
in the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church:
a comparative analysis**

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Abstract

The assessment by the Russian Orthodox Church of the war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine as a holy war prompts to determine whether this position of this Church is determined by its theological recommendations on social life, recorded in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church. The analysis of this current official document of the Russian Orthodox Church revealed that in the central part of its provisions, where the grounds for evaluating this or that war are given, there are references to the social doctrine of the Catholic Church. This fact led to the need for a comparative analysis of the instructions on war in both the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church and in the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church. Such a comparative analysis revealed that in the Compendium of the Catholic Church's social doctrine, the conditions for the legal use of force to protect against aggressors are considered, whereas in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church these conditions are considered the conditions for recognizing a war as just, even when it is waged by attackers on foreign territory. In the Catholic document, the morality of soldiers is measured by objective signs of their activity, while in the Russian Orthodox document, the morality of soldiers and the justice of their use of force is measured by their subjective inner desires. It is also determined that in the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, international organizations (such as the UN) are recognized as co-responsible for decisions to support peace and military operations, but in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, the appropriate activity within the existing organizational system of international coexistence is questioned. Therefore, it was concluded that, despite some similarity in the provisions on war in the two analyzed documents, their distinctive nuances allow and encourage different evaluations of wars, up to opposite evaluations, which is what happens among the leadership and followers of the Catholic Church and the Russian Orthodox Church in the case of the current war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine.

Keywords: Russian Orthodox Church, Catholic Church, social concept, war, defense, Ukraine.

Introduction

The news that the leadership of the Russian Orthodox Church declared the war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine a holy war¹ shocked many in the world. But this news did not come as a surprise to Ukrainians themselves. In order to understand the Basics of the position of the Russian Orthodox Church regarding Russia's war against Ukraine, it is necessary to get acquainted with the instructions regarding the problems of the war, formed in the bosom of this Church. For this, it is necessary to analyze the official document of the Russian Orthodox Church, which outlines its views on various social and public issues. "The Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church." This document was adopted by the Synod of Bishops of this Church back in August 2000, but it is still valid. Although it was stated in it that clarifications and additions could be made over time, this has not happened yet. Therefore, to this day, the formulated instructions are considered valid in the Russian Orthodox Church (hereafter ROC). They serve as a guide for clerics of this Church, as well as for clerics of the Ukrainian Orthodox Church (UOC). The UOC, despite its attempts to prove the opposite, is de facto dependent on the Moscow Patriarchate, and its edition of the Basics of Social Concept repeats the lion's share of the postulates of the original (the Basics of Social Concept Russian Orthodox Church). In this original, the reference to the social teaching of the Catholic Church on war draws attention to itself, and this makes the analysis of this issue even more urgent. After all, observing the ambiguous statements of Pope Francis also raises the question of how to correlate these statements with the social doctrine of the Catholic Church. Why and for what reason does the Russian Orthodox Church refer to the social doctrine of the Catholic Church in its Foundations of the Social Concept? How relevant are these references? Do they correspond to the original? What do the theological teachings of these two Churches have in common and differ in covering the issue of war? How is this commonality and difference is reflected in their positions regarding Russia's modern war against Ukraine?

Recent Research and Publications on this Issue

The autor attempts to find answers to these questions in this article. The proposed approach is relatively new, although previously there was no lack of researchers of theological views on war in the Russian Orthodox Church and the Catholic Church. Since we are interested in the modern context, we will note the works written by their authors — witnesses of the events of the war between Russia and Ukraine, starting from 2014. These are the works of religious scholars such as I. Zagrebelny,² L. Moiseyenko,³ O. Nedavnya,⁴ A. Babinsky,⁵ R. Golik,⁶ R. Piasta and V. Lukashevsky,⁷

1 Наказ XXV Всесвітнього російського народного собору "Сьогодні та майбутнє руського міра". [Order XXV of the World Russian People's Council "The Present and the Future of the Russian World"]. Релігійно-інформаційна служба України. Religious Information Service of Ukraine. 28 березня 2024. https://risu.ua/nakaz-xxv-vsemirnogo-russkogo-narodnogo-sobora-nastoyashchee-i-budushchee-russkogo-mira_n147172.

2 Ігор Загребельний. Апостольство меча. Християнство і застосування сили. [The apostleship of the sword. Christianity and the use of force]. Видання 3, Київ: Видавничий дім Руслана Халікова, 2024. 206 с. Edition 3, Kyiv: Ruslan Khalikov Publishing House, 2024. 206 p.; Ігор Загребельний. Християнське ставлення до війни. [Christian attitude to war]. Політична теологія. Political theology. <https://politteo.online/materialy/hrystyuyanske-stavlennya-do-vijny/>

3 Лариса Моїсеєнко. Проблеми війни та миру в трактуванні християнських конфесій. [Problems of war and peace in the interpretation of Christian confessions]. Історія релігій в Україні: науковий щорічник, 2018, Вип. 28, Ч. II. History of religions in Ukraine: scientific yearbook, 2018, issue 28, P. II. 545-565. <http://religio.org.ua/index.php/religio/article/view/252/250>

where the context of Russian military aggression is taken into account and where the features of the respective approaches of different Churches are compared. Attention should also be paid to the review of the theology of war and peace by religious authors – clergymen. Thus, in Orthodoxy, G. Kovalenko,⁸ an Orthodox clergyman who obtained a secular academic degree, studied this issue, and in Catholicism, Dominican P. Balog⁹ and a priest of the Ukrainian Greek-Catholic Church Yu. Shchurko.¹⁰ Colleagues from related scientific fields have also studied modern theological views on war, in particular, the views of the Russian Orthodox Church, e.g. V. Krysachenko, A. Zadorozhnya, Yu. Lebedeva, and Yu. Figurniy.¹¹ However, the ongoing military aggression of the Russian Federation prompts further analysis of the instructions regarding the issue of war in the basic valid document that covers them: in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, comparing them with similar (if they similar indeed?) instructions of the social doctrine of the Catholic Church.

Main Part

The content in question of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church is contained in Chapter VIII "War and Peace."¹² At the beginning of this chapter, war is declared evil, and evil is recognized as the result of people's sinful use of their God-given freedom. It is mentioned that the Gospel has evidence that there have been and will be wars in a world damaged by sin. In this respect, this fragment of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church seems to

4 Ольга Недавнія. Питання війни в соціальній доктрині Католицької Церкви через призму подій війни Росії проти України та в актуальних теологічних роздумах українських католиків. [The issue of war in the social doctrine of the Catholic Church through the prism of the events of Russia's war against Ukraine and in the actual theological reflections of Ukrainian Catholics]. *Добрий Пастир: науковий вісник Івано-Франківської академії Івана Золотоустого. Богослов'я. Філософія. Історія* / Гол. ред. Р. А. Горбань. Випуск 18. Івано-Франківськ: ІФА, 2023. *Good Parson: scientific bulletin of the Ivano-Frankivsk Academy of Ivan Zolotoustoy. Theology. Philosophy. History / Goal.* ed. R. A. Gorban. Issue 18. Ivano-Frankivsk: IFA, 2023. 142-152.

5 Анатолій Бабинський. Конфлікт концепцій. Роздуми стосовно одного інтерв'ю митрополита Іларіона (Алфеева) Релігійно-інформаційна служба України. [Conflict of concepts. Reflections on one interview of Metropolitan Hilarion (Alfeev)]. *Релігійно-інформаційна служба України. Religious Information Service of Ukraine*. 02.04.2014 https://risu.ua/konflikt-koncepciy-rozdumi-stosovno-odnogo-interv-yu-mitropolita-ilariona-alfeyeva_n68167.

6 Роман Голик. Віра як зброя: війна та релігія в культурній пам'яті XX – початку XXI ст. [Religion as a weapon: war and religion in the cultural memory of the 20th and early 21st centuries]. *Науковий щорічник "Історія релігій в Україні"*. Інститут релігієзнавства — філія Львівського музею історії. Т.1 № 32, 2022. 51-63. *Scientific yearbook "History of Religions in Ukraine"*. The Institute of Religious Studies is a branch of the Lviv Museum of History. Volume 1 No. 32, 2022. 51-63.

7 Руслан П'яста. & Володимир Лукашевський. Захист Батьківщини у вченні Католицької Церкви. [Protection of the Motherland in the teachings of the Catholic Church]. *Добрий пастир: науковий вісник Івано-Франківської академії Івана Золотоустого. Богослов'я. Філософія. Історія* / Гол. ред. Р. А. Горбань. Випуск 17. Івано-Франківськ: ІФА, 202. № 17, 2022. *Good Parson: scientific bulletin of the Ivano-Frankivsk Academy of Ivan Zolotoustoy. Theology. Philosophy. History / Goal.* ed. R. A. Gorban. Issue 17. Ivano-Frankivsk: IFA, 2022. 38-52. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.52761/2522-1558.2022.17.4> <http://journal.ifaiz.edu.ua/index.php/gp/article/view/379/395>.

8 Георгій Коваленко, протоієрей. Богослов'я війни і миру в Православній Церкві. [Theology of War and Peace in the Orthodox Church]. *Відкритий Православний університет святої Софії Премудрості. Open Orthodox University of Saint Sophia of Wisdom*. 10.02.2022 <https://oou.org.ua/2022/02/10/bogoslovya-vijny-i-myru-v-pravoslavnij-czerkvi/>

9 Петро Балог. Справедлива війна. [Just War]. *Християнська служба порятунку. Christian Rescue Service*. <http://crs-center.org/spravedlyva-vijna>.

10 Щурко Юрій, о. Наївність пацифізму та принципи ведення справедливої війни. [The naivety of pacifism and the principles of waging a just war]. *CREDO*. 09.05.2022. <https://credo.pro/2022/05/319079>.

11 Valentyn Krysachenko; Alina Zadorozhnya; Yulia Lebedeva; and Yuriy Figurniy (2023) "Russian Orthodox Church as Apologist for the Current Russian Aggression," *Occasional Papers on Religion in Eastern Europe*: Vol. 43 : Iss. 4, Article 2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55221/2693-2148.2426> Available at: <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/ree/vol43/iss4/2>.

12 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 26-29.

coincide with a similar fragment of the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, where it is written that as long as there is sin in the world, wars are generated by it. However, later in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church there are explanations that can be interpreted as a certain justification for the fact that the situation of wars on earth will last forever: earthly wars reflect the heavenly struggle, which is generated by pride and denial of the will of God.

Such an assumption about a "loophole for justification" is strengthened upon analyzing the subsequent text of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church. There, it is emphasized that murders that accompany any war were recognized as a grave crime before God already at the beginning of sacred history. At the same time, Christians, who deliver the message of reconciliation to the earthly world, live in a sinful world, full of evil and violence, therefore, in order to survive, they have to take part in various wars. Let us pay attention – it is claimed that Christians have to (which means “may”) take part in "various" wars¹³ (does it also mean, in offensive, invading ones?)

In contrast, Subsection 3 of Chapter 11, "The Failure of Peace: War"¹⁴ of the Compendium of Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church unequivocally states that aggressive war is inherently immoral. It is noteworthy that the entire Chapter 11 of the Compendium, dealing with the problems of war, is titled "The Promotion of Peace." It is important that the Compendium considers the war situation from the position of the contemporaries of the era of atomic weapons: for Catholics, “it is difficult to imagine that in the atomic age war would be used as an instrument of justice,”¹⁵ so it is emphasized that war can never contribute to the resolution of problems between nations, that it is a needless massacre and a no-win adventure that affects the present and threatens the future of humankind, and that war is the downfall of all true humanism and is always a defeat for humanity.

In the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, referring to the authority of the Holy Scripture, it is explained that participation in military operations does not contradict the instruction about love and prayer for enemies and "turning the other cheek." It is claimed that the Bible talks about not resisting individual harm, instead for community life, there is another instruction that exalts the virtue of protecting neighbors and elevates fallen defenders to the rank of holy martyrs and supplicants before God.¹⁶ Of course, Catholics also mention the dilemma of the “other cheek” in their reflections on the use of force for Christians, but in the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, attention is focused on specific actions aimed at preventing harm and preventing war, or at least at observing certain frameworks of morality in its course.

It is worth noting that the text of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church is characterized by the use of phrases that allow for ambiguous interpretations. This, in particular, refers to the explanation of why this Church does not forbid its believers to participate in military actions, if it is about protecting neighbors and restoring violated justice: they say, in this case war is a forced, although undesirable, remedy.¹⁷ At the same time, what justice is in question and who these neighbors are (compatriots, fellow citizens, fellow believers, and where do they live?) is not

13 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 26.

14 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church]*. К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Kyiv: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 303-306.

15 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church]*. К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Kyiv: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 303.

16 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 26-27.

17 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 26.

specified. The list of neighbors, thus, can be defined in any way, and in practice – are all relatives asked whether they want protection, and whose protection? Using the example of the invasion of Russian troops into Ukraine, we can state that these questions are rhetorical.

However, to substantiate their instructions regarding a just war, the authors of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church do not only refer to the authority of the Bible (all they that take the sword shall perish with the sword). E.g., it is claimed that the position of the Christian Church regarding moral truth in international relations (which is based on three principles: love for one's neighbors, one's people, and the Motherland, understanding the needs of other nations, and the conviction that the good of one's nation cannot be served by immoral means) back in the Middle Ages influenced the determination of the morally acceptable framework of war. It is emphasized that since then there was a conviction: the war should be conducted according to certain rules and the soldiers should not neglect the norms of morality in the fight against the enemy.¹⁸ It is added that the demand for justice for the warriors was not always fulfilled, but the very question of justice at least partially restrained them from great cruelty. In the text of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, it is rightly noted that such an approach could be formed under the influence of Christianity, but the fact that it is a fruit and was applied (although not always and not completely) by European, Western Christian nations, is ignored.

The latter becomes clear already from the next paragraph of the analyzed section of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, which appeals to the developments of Western Christian theology. These developments are referred to when it comes to specific definitions of the signs of a just war. Thus, in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church the factors that, as it is claimed, according to the Western Christian theology, determine the permissibility of starting a war on one's own or alien's territory, are listed: war should be declared in order to restore justice only; only the legitimate government has the right to declare war; the right to use force should not belong to individuals or their groups, but to representatives of civil power established from above; war can be declared only after all peaceful means of negotiating with the opposing side and restoring the initial situation have been exhausted; war should be declared only if there is a fully justified hope of achieving the adopted goal; planned military losses and destruction must correspond to the situation and goals of the war (principle of proportionality of means); during the war, the civilian population should be protected from direct military actions; war can be justified only by the desire to restore peace and order.¹⁹

Let us compare these points with the formulation of signs that determine the just character of military actions in the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church. Thus, in the relevant subsection of the Compendium, titled "Legitimate defense."²⁰ the conditions of legal defense with the help of military force are considered. It is argued that the leaders of an attacked state have the right and duty to defend the country, including by force of arms. At the same time, it is emphasized: "it is one thing to wage a war of self-defense; it is quite another to seek to impose domination on another nation."²¹ The use of force is recognized as legal if it meets certain strict conditions, in particular: "the damage inflicted by the aggressor on the nation or community of nations must be

18 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 27.

19 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 27.

20 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church]*. К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Kyiv: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 305-306.

21 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church]*. К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Kyiv: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 306.

lasting, grave and certain; all other means of putting an end to it must have been shown to be impractical or ineffective; there must be serious prospects of success; the use of arms must not produce evils and disorders graver than the evil to be eliminated."²² The Compendium also states that the power of modern means of destruction should be taken into account when evaluating these conditions, and mentions that these are the traditional elements listed in the doctrine of the so-called "just war". However, the term "just war" is not applied further and no references are given to this doctrine as approved in any current official document of the Catholic Church. Instead, it is emphasized that the assessment of the conditions of moral legitimacy belongs to the discretion of those who are responsible for the common good.

As we can see, in the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, in contrast to the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, the emphasis is made on the justice and legality of defense, not war. In the document of the Russian Orthodox Church, the instructions borrowed from Catholic theology differ in nuances and contain certain additions that can be interpreted in a manipulative manner. Therefore, the reference to the authority of Western Christian theology is rather used here to reinforce or justify seemingly similar, but somewhat different instructions, which are reformulated to suit Russian interests.

The difference in how the capabilities and activities of international organizations are assessed in the context of the issue of war in the two analyzed documents is notable. In the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, we find a reference to the authority of international organizations and assigning them part of the responsibility for the peaceful coexistence of nations. Indeed, "States do not always possess adequate means to provide effectively for their own defense, from this derives the need and importance of international and regional organizations, which should be in a position to work together to resolve conflicts and promote peace, re-establishing relationships of mutual trust that make recourse to war unthinkable."²³ Therefore, the UN Charter prohibits the use of force to resolve conflicting issues between states, with the exception of two cases: necessary protection and measures taken by the Security Council within its competence to establish peace. At the same time, it is noted that preventive military actions, which do not have motivational grounds, give rise to serious moral and legal problems. Therefore, it is concluded that only the competent authorities, after determined it on the basis of a thorough assessment and a serious justification of the threat to peace, can give international permission for the use of weapons. Therefore, it is emphasized that it is very important to increase the number of military personnel who serve in international forces, carrying out humanitarian or peacekeeping missions of the UN.

The international community is called upon to respond to genocide: it "has the moral obligation to intervene on behalf of those groups whose very survival is threatened or whose basic human rights are seriously violated. As members of an international community, States cannot remain indifferent; on the contrary, if all other available means should prove ineffective, it is legitimate and even obligatory to take concrete measures to disarm the aggressor."²⁴ In addition, the paragraph "Measures against those who threaten peace" refers to sanctions provided for by the modern international order, which are intended to correct the behavior of the governments of countries that violate the rules of peaceful and organized international coexistence.

22 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church].* К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Київ: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 305.

23 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church].* К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Київ: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 305.

24 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church].* К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Київ: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 308-309.

Instead, in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, the current organization of the system of international relations is questioned: they say, in the existing realities, it is difficult to distinguish an aggressive war from a defensive one. Moreover, it is argued that the line between aggressive and defensive war is especially thin if some state, several states or the world community initiates military actions, motivated by the need to protect the nation, which is a victim of aggression.²⁵ In the circumstances of the modern war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, such a statement resembles a preemptive condemnation of the aid of allies to Ukraine, which was attacked by Russia. Therefore, in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church it is concluded that the Church should consider the issue of support or condemnation of a specific war in each case of its start or threat of start.

It is noteworthy that in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, the emphasis shifts from the definition of one or another war in general to the righteousness or unrighteousness of the warriors. According to the guidelines of the Concept, the righteousness or unrighteousness of warriors is indicated by the methods by which they fight and their treatment of prisoners and civilians. With reference to the Bible, it is argued that war should be fought with righteous anger, but not with malice, greed and lust. However, in a war of aggression, who can and will determine whether the treatment of prisoners and the civilian population is truly humane? In general, in such a war, the military men are not righteous, since such a war is clearly unjust. However, in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, it is claimed that, if you do not allow evil into your heart, you gain the possibility of fair use of force. It is emphasized that the moral Christian law condemns not the fight against evil, not the use of force against the bearer of evil and not even his murder, but the malice of the heart and the desire to destroy anyone.²⁶ As the practice of the modern war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine shows, such instructions could be easily interpreted as beneficial to the attackers: they say, they are not evil but just wage a holy war not against the general population, but against Nazis and aggressive NATO members.

In contrast, in the text of the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, the moral requirements for soldiers are spelled out specifically: "Every member of the armed forces is morally obliged to resist orders that call for perpetrating crimes against the law of nations and the universal principles of this law. Military personnel remain fully responsible for the acts they commit in violation of the rights of individuals and peoples, or of the norms of international humanitarian law. Such acts cannot be justified by claiming obedience to the orders of superiors."²⁷ In the section of the Compendium titled "The duty to protect the innocent" it is emphasized that "Attempts to eliminate entire national, ethnic, religious or linguistic groups are crimes against God and humanity itself, and those responsible for such crimes must answer for them before justice."²⁸ Examples of criminal genocides are given, including the genocide of Ukrainians.

The provisions of the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church state that any military action aimed at destroying entire cities or regions, together with their inhabitants, is a crime against God and people. There, terror, which has become a new way of waging war, is condemned and it is emphasized that those who commit it under the guise of the name of God commit

25 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 27.

26 *Основы социальной концепции Русской Православной Церкви. [Basics of the social concept of the Russian Orthodox Church]* https://www.scribd.com/fullscreen/28004295?access_key=key-1tmrtxcej3i0cqo5cw8t. 28.

27 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church]*. К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Kyiv: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 307.

28 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church]*. К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Kyiv: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 308.

sacrilege.²⁹ Such instructions are absent in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church. Such instructions are absent in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church. Instead, a recent example of declaring armed aggression against Ukraine a holy war demonstrates just such a guise of the name of God for an offensive, invasive war, in which the Russian army is trying to destroy the entire population of Ukraine, including civilians, entire cities and regions, which could not be approved by any doctrine of just or holy war.

Conclusions

The above comparative analysis of provisions about the war of two valid official documents, the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church and the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. In the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, evaluations of war in terms of its justice or injustice are replaced by evaluations of the righteousness or unrighteousness of the soldiers themselves, and the definition of the latter comes down not to whether they are or are not attackers and invaders, but to whether they have or do not have evil in the heart and willing or unwilling to destroy anyone. Instead, the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church examines the justice (as legality, according to accepted international laws) not of war as such, but of protection against aggressors.

2. In the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, the signs necessary for the lawful use of force are given, and it is about the force that is used for defense against attackers, while in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, the relevant textual fragment of the Catholic social doctrine, being tendentiously interpreted and supplemented, is used in the justification of the possible justice of the war in general.

3. Both documents talk about the necessary morality of soldiers, about the humane treatment of enemies, captives and the civilian population, but the text of the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church lacks the caveat found in the Compendium of Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church regarding the personal responsibility of each soldier to resist and not fulfill criminal orders of their leadership.

4. In the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Catholic Church, international organizations and their peace-making efforts are respected; a part of the responsibility for maintaining peace and the just and lawful use of force is assigned to international organizations. On the other hand, in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church, the system of organizing international coexistence, including its military decisions, is questionable.

5. The seeming similarity of part of the social instructions in the two analyzed documents is leveled in the Basics of the Social Concept of the Russian Orthodox Church by the dissimilar deployment of other instructions, and their appeal to (self-interestedly read) fragments of the social doctrine of the Catholic Church are involved rather to justify their own, imperial views on war, soldiers, and opponents.

6. The instructions of the social doctrine of the Catholic Church contain all the necessary provisions for condemning the war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, which the Apostolic See is essentially doing, while the social instructions of the Russian Orthodox Church are formulated in such a way that they allow tolerance and even approval and sanctification of this war, which indeed took place.

29 *Компендіум соціальної доктрини Церкви. [Compendium of the social doctrine of the Church].* К.: Кайрос, 2008. 549 с. Kyiv: Kairos. 2004. 549 p. 313.

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